

INFLUENCE OF ULTRASONIC RADIATION ON INTERCALATION OF GRAPHITE WITH MICROCLUSTER WATER

Yurov V.

*Candidate of phys.-mat. sciences, associate professor
KarTU, Karaganda, Kazakhstan*

Zhangozin K.

*Candidate of phys.-mat. sciences, associate professor
TSK Vostok LLP, Ust-Kamenogorsk, Republic of Kazakhstan,*

Kargin D.

*Candidate of Physical and Mathematical Sciences, Associate Professor
NAO "L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University",
Astana, Kazakhstan*

ABSTRACT

The article presents a model of the thickness of the surface layer of water, from which its cluster structure flows. The presence of vibrations or ultrasound leads to the stratification of graphite into thin plates or flakes. The magnitude of these effects depends on their power and the surface tension of the liquid. A model of the splitting of graphite with water is constructed as a Stefan problem with a moving phase boundary.

Keywords: Graphite, graphene, surface layer, nanostructure, ultrasound, delamination, crystal.

Introduction

To obtain graphene, graphite must be split. The first successful splitting of graphite by ultrasonic treatment was achieved in the organic solvent N-methylpyrrolidone [1]. It was also proposed to exfoliate graphite by ultrasonic treatment in the presence of surface-active substances (surfactants). This was first reported in [2], where dodecylbenzenesulfonate was used as a surfactant. In [3, 4], it was shown that graphene structures obtained by ultrasonic treatment of graphite and its de-

rivatives contain a lot of oxygen. In [5], multilayer graphene was obtained by ultrasonic splitting of graphite microparticles in a surface-active solvent, a mixture of nonane and water, a surface-active surfactant was selected that ensures dispersion of graphene in hydrophilic systems. In [6], a technology was developed for obtaining polymers modified with graphene structures using ultrasonic dispersion (Fig. 1). A complete review of methods for obtaining graphene by splitting graphite is given in [7-10].

Figure 1. Schematic (a) and external view (b) of the ultrasonic unit of the setup for liquid-phase exfoliation of graphite [6].

The aim of this article is a theoretical model of graphite intercalation with microcluster water in ultrasound.

Intercalation of graphite with microcluster wa-

ter

We obtained graphene nanoflakes by intercalation of graphite with microcluster water (MKW) (Fig. 1) [11-13].

Figure 2. Intercalation of graphite MKW (a); graphene nanoflakes (b).

The essence of this process is as follows: MKW is obtained using the method described in [14, 15]; then the MKW is introduced into the interlayer space of graphite, followed by the production of graphene flakes. Let us first consider the structure of cluster water.

Cluster water

Graphite practically does not react in pure water. Its layered structure does not allow water molecules to penetrate between the graphite layers. Therefore,

graphite remains stable and does not dissolve [16]. In 1993, Ken Jordan proposed his own versions of stable "water quanta" consisting of 6 of its molecules [17]. Subsequent experiments and ab initio calculations made it possible to find out more about the cluster structure of water [18-20]. In their opinion, the composition of water clusters consists of 3 to 50 water molecules each (Fig. 3). A review of the cluster structure of water is given in [21].

Figure 3. Clusters in the structure of water [21].

Two Patents (Lorenzen L.H.) more than 20 years ago described the process of obtaining microcluster water [14, 15]. First, the source water is boiled to produce

steam. Next, the steam is passed through a magnetic field and the steam is condensed at a temperature above

0 °C in the presence of light in the range from far infrared to ultraviolet spectrum. At least one metasilicate salt stabilizer and a food additive template are added to the condensed steam. The concentration of the food additive is about 1%. The condensed steam is subjected to a pressure of more than 1 atm., and then the pressure is released to produce microcluster water. Microcluster water gives a resonance NMR signal 170 at 115 HZ, has a conductivity of at least 3.7 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and a surface tension of less than 61 dynes/cm.

Dr. Hidemitsu Hayashi [22] in February 2023 published an article against the cluster structure of water. The most commonly used evidence is the results of nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) [14, 15]. The idea is that the larger the width of its band, the larger the water cluster. At first glance, this seems quite convincing. However, the problem is that the width of the band depends on the pH [22], not on the size of the cluster. Any deviation from neutral pH in either direction will lead to a similar result [22]. Dr. Hidemitsu Hayashi argues that so far there has been no convincing evidence from a physical and chemical point of view for the existence of stable water microclusters, and research in this field has consistently refuted this claim, which is not surprising, since this claim contradicts the basic and fundamental principles of chemistry.

What do we assume about cluster water in this article? According to Rusanov A.I., the thickness of the surface layer should be understood as a layer of water that is electrically neutral and has a size of 1-2 nm [23]. According to Ken Jordan's idea [17], this layer of water consists of 6 of its molecules ($6 \times 0.193 = 1.15 \text{ nm}$). In [24], we obtained $R(I) = 1.1 \text{ nm}$ for the thickness of the surface layer of water. This means that the number of monolayers in the layer $R(I)$ is equal to $n = R(I)/a$ ($a = 0.193 \text{ nm}$ is the radius of the water molecule) ≈ 6 . We can conclude that the thickness of the surface layer of water meets the condition of Rusanov A.I. [23] and the clusters of Ken Jordan [19]. In other words, the cluster structure of water, like all liquids, is a physical phenomenon caused by the difference in the interaction of atoms on the surface and in the volume. For liquids, mixing of layers leads to a cluster structure of most of it.

Intercalation of graphite with MKW with a centrifuge

The experiment (Fig. 4) consisted of centrifuging the samples at 4000 rpm. Graphite powder (natural graphite grade GL-1) weighing 6 g was poured into both vessels, MKW was poured into one vessel, and distilled [11] into the second vessel. The result is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 4. Scheme of the experiment with a centrifuge [11].

a)
b)
Figure 5. Vessels before (a) and after (b) centrifugation: left (MKW) and right (distilled water)

After centrifugation for 60 minutes, the level of the microcrystalline oxide decreases. Fig. 5b shows the vessels after centrifugation. It is evident that the level of the microcrystalline oxide has decreased significantly, to 12 mm. The intercalation process occurs in a certain sequence. At first, the adsorption of intercalated particles on the outer plane of graphite occurs, which is accompanied by a charge transfer from the carbon plane to the adsorbed particle. The layers adjacent to the outer surface are the first to open for intercalation;

their filling leads to the opening of adjacent layers and their filling with intercalants. Thus, intercalation is a staged process that occurs along the normal to the base plane of graphite. Centrifugation accelerates this intercalation process.

Ultrasound in the “water-graphite” system

Ultrasonic (US) dispersion of natural [25] and thermally expanded graphite [26, 27] in the “liquid-graphite” system was carried out in solvents – water, acetonitrile, toluene, orthoxylene (Fig. 6).

a)
b)
Figure 6. Dependences of the time of 50% sedimentation of nanographite particles in different solvents on the time of ultrasonic treatment (a); SEM image of nanographite (b) [25].

It is evident from Fig. 6 that the optimal system is the “water-graphite” system, which we will discuss further. The source was an ultrasonic bath PSB-Gals (with a piezoceramic transducer) with an operating frequency of 50 kHz, a specific power of ultrasonic action of 0.03 W/ml. The suspension was processed for 60 min at a temperature of 22±2 °C. The main effect of ultrasonic

action on water is cavitation. Acoustic cavitation can cause both isotropic and anisotropic collapse of bubbles in water, which leads to shock waves and microjets (Fig. 7) [28, 29]. Compared with mechanical stirring, ultrasonic short-term cavitation (bubble collapse) can generate microjets with a speed of about 110 m/s and also with a large impact force.

(a) Isotropic bubble collapse and shock wave propagation

(b) Anisotropic cavitation of microjet at a wall surface

Figure 7. Schematic diagram of a shock wave (a) and a microjet (b) formed during the collapse of a cavitation bubble [28, 29].

Let us consider this issue theoretically as a Stefan problem, using the analytical solution of the non-stationary problem obtained by us in [30, 31]. Let us consider a model of the transport flow of an aqueous solution through graphite placed in a cylindrical glass in an ultrasonic field.

Let us choose boundary conditions in the simplest periodic form. In this case, the diffusion problem has the boundary conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} &= \ddot{A} \left[\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial C}{\partial r} \right) \right] \\ C(r, z, t) \Big|_{t=0} &= \varphi(r, z) \\ C(r, z, t) \Big|_{t=R} &= \gamma(z, t) = C_0 \sin \omega t \sin \mathbf{kr}, \\ C(r, z, t) \Big|_{z=0} &= \gamma_1(r, t) = C_1 \sin \omega t \sin \mathbf{kr}, \\ C(r, z, t) \Big|_{z=\beta(t)} &= \gamma_2(r, t) = C_2 \sin \omega t \sin \mathbf{kr}. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where C_0, C_1, C_2 are the concentrations of the graphite substance on the side walls of the water-graphite system and on the moving phase boundary, respectively; ω, k are the cyclic frequency of the disturbing ultrasonic field and the wave vector.

We have given a general solution to this problem in [30, 31]:

$$\begin{aligned} C(r, z, t) &= \sum_{\xi=0}^{\infty} J_0(\lambda_{\xi} r) \left\{ e^{\ddot{A}t} \left[\frac{1}{2\sqrt{\ddot{A}\pi}} \int_0^t e^{-\frac{(z-\xi)^2}{4\ddot{A}\tau}} d\tau \right. \right. \\ &\times \left(\int_0^{\ell} \varphi(r, \xi) I_0(\lambda_{ok} r) r dr \right) d\xi + \frac{RI_1(\lambda_{ok} R)}{2\sqrt{\ddot{A}\pi}} \int_0^t d\tau \int_0^{\ell} \frac{\gamma(\xi, \tau)}{\sqrt{t-\tau}} e^{-\ddot{A}t} e^{-\frac{(z-\xi)^2}{4\ddot{A}(t-\tau)}} d\xi + \\ &\left. \left. + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^t \frac{z}{[\ddot{A}(t-\tau)]^{3/2}} e^{-\frac{z^2}{4\ddot{A}(t-\tau)}} K_1(\tau) d\tau + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^t \frac{z-\beta(\tau)}{[\ddot{A}(t-\tau)]^{3/2}} e^{-\frac{[z-\beta(\tau)]^2}{4\ddot{A}(t-\tau)}} K_2(\tau) d\tau \right] \right\}. \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

On the z-axis and at $r=0$, we have

$$\dot{N}(z, t) = \frac{1}{4\sqrt{\pi}} \left(\int_0^t \frac{z}{[\ddot{A}(t-\tau)]^3} e^{-\frac{z^2}{4\ddot{A}(t-\tau)}} K_1(\tau) d\tau + \int_0^t \frac{z-\beta(\tau)}{[\ddot{A}(t-\tau)]^3} e^{-\frac{[z-\beta(\tau)]^2}{4\ddot{A}(t-\tau)}} K_2(\tau) d\tau \right) \quad (3)$$

Taking $\beta(\tau)=H$ (i.e. for a finite cylinder of depth H and radius R), calculating $K_1(\tau)$ and $K_2(\tau)$, for the axial concentration gradient we have:

$$\partial \dot{N} / \partial z = \frac{8\pi v}{\lambda} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{\ddot{A}}} e^{-\frac{(z-h)^2}{4\ddot{A}} t} (\dot{N}_1 + \dot{N}_2). \quad (4)$$

where v, λ are the speed and wavelength of the alternating field; h is the distance to the horizontal plane coinciding with the average cross-section of the source of the excited field.

Let us designate:

$$W = \frac{8\pi v}{\lambda} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{\ddot{A}}} (C_1 + C_2). \quad (5)$$

Finally, we can write:

$$\partial \dot{N} / \partial z = W \cdot e^{-\frac{(z-h)^2}{4\ddot{A}} t}. \quad (6)$$

From formula (6) it follows that the presence of periodic boundary conditions simulating periodic ultrasonic action on the "water-graphite" system leads to an exponential law of change in the vertical component of concentration, where:

$$v = \frac{\omega \lambda}{2\pi}. \quad (7)$$

In other words, graphite intercalation will increase in the system "liquid-graphite" with an increase in the ultrasound power $\sim v$ and the surface tension of the liquid $\sim \gamma$. The latter dependence follows from equation (5). According to the classical Newtonian theory [32], $D = \nu$, where ν is the kinematic viscosity coefficient. We have shown [13] that $\nu \sim 1/\gamma$ and therefore $W \sim \gamma^{1/2}$. Let us present some values of γ for some liquids [32].

Table 1.

Surface tension of liquids at 20 °C

Liquid	$\gamma, 10^{-3} \text{ N/m}$	Liquid	$\gamma, 10^{-3} \text{ N/m}$	Liquid	$\gamma, 10^{-3} \text{ N/m}$
water	72,75	glycerol	63,40	chloroform	27,14
acetonitrile	26,64	phenol	40,90	benzene	28,88
toluene	28,40	acetone	23,70	ethyl acetate	23,60
orthoxylyene	30,10	ethanol	22,80	mercury	465,0

It follows from Table 1 that water has the highest γ value (except mercury) and surpasses all liquids in the ultrasonic splitting of graphite (Fig. 6a) for the purpose of obtaining graphene plates from it. To determine the thickness of graphene plates, it is necessary to use Raman scattering and the corresponding equipment. Ultrasonic splitting of graphite is similar to the effect of a centrifuge (Figs. 4 and 5), but it is much more effective since it is possible to use the effect of cavitation of water bubbles.

Conclusion

The effect of ultrasound on graphite splitting is far from complete. Particular attention should be paid to the theory of cavitation and its nonlinearity. Graphite splitting is the destruction of solids, where it is necessary to apply the theory of catastrophes. When graphite splits, many new planes appear that differ significantly from the properties of bulk graphite. This list can be continued, but the main thing is to obtain graphene plates or flakes suitable for their practical application.

This scientific article was published as part of grant funding for 2024-2026, IRN No. AR32488258 "Development of innovative technology for producing graphene by intercalating graphite with microcluster water and modifying HTSC ceramics with graphene" (the research is funded by the Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan).

References

1. Hernandez Y., Nicolosi V., Lotya M., Blighe F.M., Sun Z.Y., De S., McGovern I.T., Holland B., Byrne M., Gun'ko Y.K., Boland J.J., Niraj P., Duesberg

G., Krishnamurthy S., Goodhue R., Hutchison J., Scardaci V., Ferrari A. C. High-yield production of graphene by liquid-phase exfoliation of graphite // Nature Nanotechnology, 2008, V. 3, № 9. - P. 563-568.

2. Lotya M., Hernandez Y., King P.J., Smith R.J., Nicolosi V., Karlsson L.S., Blighe F.M., De S., Wang Z.M., McGovern I.T., Duesberg G.S., Coleman J.N. Liquid Phase Production of Graphene by Exfoliation of Graphite in Surfactant/Water Solutions // Journal of the American Chemical Society, 2009, V. 131, № 10. - P. 3611-3620.

3. Skaltsas T., Ke X.X., Bittencourt C., Tagmatarchis N. Ultrasonication Induces Oxygenated Species and Defects onto Exfoliated Graphene // Journal of Physical Chemistry C., 2013, V. 117, № 44. - P. 23272-23278.

4. Bracamonte M.V., Lacconi G.I., Urreta S.E., Torres L. On the Nature of Defects in Liquid-Phase Exfoliated Graphene // Journal of Physical Chemistry C., 2014, V. 118, № 28. - P. 15455-15459.

5. Denisjuk I.Yu., Logushkova K.Yu., Fokina M.I., Uspenskaya M.V. FT-IR spectra of multilayer graphene and its composition with a surfactant // Optics and Spectroscopy, 2019, Vol. 126, Issue 2. - P. 177-179.

6. Rubanik V.V., Savitsky V.O., Rubanik V.V.ml., Lutsko V.F., Nikiforova I.V., Bui H.T., Doan D.F. Obtaining graphene structures and nanopolymers using ultrasonic vibrations // Vector of Science TSU. 2021. No. 3. - P. 74-83.

7. Sattler K.D. (Editor). Carbon nanomaterials sourcebook. Graphene, Fullerenes, Nanotubes and Nanodiamonds. - CRC Press. - 2016. - 561 p.

8. Penkov O.V. Graphene. Simulation Methods, Preparation Methods, and their Applications. – Elsevier. - 2020. – 247 p.
9. Swain B.P. (Editor). Nanostructured Materials and their Applications. - Springer Nature Singapore Pte Ltd. - 2021. – 434 p.
10. Zhang T. Graphene. From Theory to Applications. – Springerю. - 2022. – 142 p.
11. Zhangozin K.N. New method for producing graphene by intercalation of graphite with microcluster water. - Almaty: Darkhan, 2023. – 102 p.
12. Yurov V., Zhangozin K. About the mechanism of graphite splitting // International independent scientific journal, 2024, №58. – P. 29-40.
13. Yurov V.M., Zhangozin K.N. At the mechanism of graphite splitting bouby aqueous solutions // Znanstvena misel journal, 2024, №86. – P. 41-49.
14. Lorenzen L.H. Process for preparing microclustered water. Patent Number: 5,711,95. Date of Patent: Jan. 27, 1998.
15. Lorenzen L.H. Microclustered water. Patent Number: 6,033,678. Date of Patent: Mar. 7, 2000.
16. Ubbelohde A.R., Lewis F.A. Graphite and its crystalline compounds. – M.: Mir, 1965. – 256 p.
17. Tsai C.J. and Jordan K.D. Theoretical Study of the (H₂O)₆ Cluster // Chemical Physics Letters. – 1993. - V. 213. - P. 181-188.
18. Nilsson A., Pettersson L.G.M. Perspective on the structure of liquid water // Chemical Physics. – 2011. - V. 389. – P. 1-34.
19. Ignatov I., Mosin O.V., Velikov B. Mathematical models describing the structure of water // Internet journal "Science Studies". - 2013. - No. 3. - P. 1-26.
20. Chen M, Ko H.-Yu, Remsing R.C. and etc. Ab initio theory and modeling of water // PNAS. – 2017. - Vol. 114. - No. 41. – P. 1-12.
21. Chaplin M.F. Structure and Properties of Water in its Various States. Encyclopedia of Water: Science, Technology, and Society, edited by Patricia A. Maurice. 2019. – P. 1-19.
22. Hidemitsu Hayashi. Microclustering: the making of a myth. - February 5. - 2023.
23. Rusanov A.I. Surface forces and boundary layers of liquids. – M.: Nauka. - 1983. – 152 p.
24. Yurov V.M., Zhangozin K.N. Thickness of the surface layer of water and ethanol // Physicochemical aspects of the study of clusters, nanostructures and nanomaterials. - 2023. - Issue. 15. - P. 338-349.
25. Ioni Yu.V., Tkachev S.V., Bulychev N.A., Gubin S.P. Production of ultradispersed nanographite // Inorganic materials. - 2011. - Vol. 47. - No. 6. - P. 671–677.
26. Zhanakhova A.N., Negutorov N.V., Pykhova N.V., Dyskina B.Sh. Features of ultrasonic dispersion of thermally expanded graphite // Izvestiya. vuzov. Chemistry and chemical technology. - 2020. - Vol. 63. - Issue. 2. - P. 46-51.
27. Kastsova A.G., Glebova N.V., Nechitailov A.A., Krasnova A.O., Pelageikina A.O., Eliseev I.A. Electron spectroscopy of graphene obtained by ultrasonic dispersion // Letters to the Journal of Technical Physics. - 2022. – Vol. 48. - Issue 24. - P. 23-25.
28. Kim Y.C., Min H., Yu J., Hong S.Y., Wang M., Kim S.H., Suhr J., Lee Y.K., Kim K.J., Nam J. Forced infiltration of silica beads into densely-packed glass fibre beds for thin composite laminates // RSC Adv. – 2016. - Vol. 6. – P. 91341–91348.
29. Ren X., Tong Z., Dai Y., Ma G., Lv Z., Bu X., Bilal M., Vakyabad A.B., Hassanzadeh A. Effects of Mechanical Stirring and Ultrasound Treatment on the Separation of Graphite Electrode Materials from Copper Foils of Spent LIBs: A Comparative Study // Separations. – 2023. - Vol. 10. 246.
30. Yurov V.M., Kuketaev T.A. Crystallization of a cylinder of finite dimensions // Handbook of the depository at VINITI. 1982. - No. 6485-82 Dep.
31. Yurov V.M., Platova E.S., Guchenko S.A. Corrosion and Stefan's problem // Sciences of Europe. – 2019. - No. 45(2). – P. 48-53.
32. Strelkov S.P. Mechanics. - St. Petersburg: Lan, 2005. - 560 p.
33. Krylov A.B. Surface tension and related phenomena. - Minsk: BSMU. - 2008. - 32 p.
34. Yurov V.M., Zhangozin K.N. Splitting of graphite by microcluster water // A collection of articles prepared on the basis of reports of the International scientific and practical conference "Structural modernization of science as a basis for sustainable development of society", held on April 15, 2024 in Tyumen. - P. 32-46.
35. Yurov V.M., Zhangozin K.N., Zhanabergenov T.K., Kargin D.B. Surface phenomena in graphite and obtaining graphene from it // Science News of Kazakhstan, 2024, No. 1. - P. 11-23.